

Extreme weather events and environmental contamination under climate change: A comparative review of ten European coastal cities

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Climate change intensifies extreme weather events. Their impacts on environmental contamination are investigated in ten European coastal cities, spanning diverse climatic regions: Sligo (Ireland), Dublin (Ireland), Vilanova (Spain), Benidorm (Spain), Oarsoaldea (Spain), Massa (Italy), Oeiras (Portugal), Piran (Slovenia), Gdansk (Poland) and Samsun (Turkey). Rising sea levels and storm surges, heavy precipitation and flooding, and other climate hazards exacerbate the mobilization of contaminants from natural and anthropogenic sources (agricultural runoff, industrial discharges and urban effluents). By examining the interactions between extreme weather events and contaminant pathways, this study highlights heightened risks to public health, ecosystems and water quality. Case studies demonstrate the compound effects of flooding, coastal erosion and droughts on contamination dynamics: untreated wastewater overflow, release of sediments and landfill contaminants, elevated pollutant concentrations, saltwater intrusion and algal blooms. Mitigation and adaptation strategies are discussed, including monitoring and early warning systems, sustainable urban drainage infrastructure, nature-based solutions and policy frameworks.

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Introduction

The accelerating impacts of climate change are reshaping environmental dynamics, particularly in coastal cities, which face increased vulnerability due to rising seas and extreme weather events [1,2]. In Europe, the region where this review is focused, coastal cities are witnessing more frequent storms, floods, heatwaves, and droughts [3,4], all of which exacerbate environmental contamination [5,6]. Climate change alters the fate and transport of various contaminants—including heavy metals, microplastics, and microbial pathogens—, impacting aquatic and terrestrial systems [7].

Coastal cities are uniquely challenged by a combination of natural and human-induced pressures [8,9]. Urbanization, tourism, industrial activities, and agricultural runoff contribute to contamination, with extreme weather events amplifying pollutant mobilization and transport [10,11]. For instance, floods resuspend sediment-bound heavy metals and transport microplastics from urban runoff, potentially increasing their toxicity. These interactions pose severe risks to ecosystems, water quality and public health. In addition, adaptation strategies in urban resilience efforts sometimes yield unintended consequences, such as the release of contaminants during poorly planned infrastructure interventions or the over-reliance on hard engineering solutions, which can exacerbate erosion or ecosystem degradation.

This review examines the impacts of climate-related hazards on contamination in ten European coastal cities—Sligo, Dublin, Vilanova i la Geltrú, Benidorm, Oarsoaldea, Massa, Oeiras, Piran, Gdansk, and Samsun—spanning regions from the Atlantic to the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black Seas, with a focus on surface waters. It explores the contamination risks these cities face in relation to the climate-related hazards previously identified [3,12], highlights strategies for mitigating the effects of climate change, and identifies areas for further research (Fig. 1).

Overview of climate impacts and extreme weather in the cities

This review examines ten European coastal cities—Sligo (Ireland), Dublin (Ireland), Vilanova i la Geltrú

Figure 1

Review structure, including the location of study cities and extreme weather events contributing to contamination risk.

(Spain), Benidorm (Spain), Oarsoaldea (Spain), Massa (Italy), Oeiras (Portugal), Piran (Slovenia), Gdansk (Poland), and Samsun (Türkiye)—which face unique climate challenges [12]. These cities were selected for their geographic, climatic, and socioeconomic diversity, as well as their vulnerability to extreme weather events and distinct contamination risks. Additionally, their initiative and commitment to building innovative climate resilience solutions are exemplified by their proactive participation in collaborative climate adaptation efforts, such as those associated with the SCORE project.

Data collection for each city was conducted through a participatory process encompassing an extensive literature review and direct engagement with local stakeholders [3,12]. This included workshops, questionnaires, and meetings involving municipal authorities, local organizations, and regional experts. Specific publications covering the research topic were retrieved from the Scopus database to build on the previous baseline information. Publications were systematically retrieved using search terms such as “climate change,” “pollution,” “contaminants,” and “extreme weather events.” After retrieval, publications were manually filtered to ensure relevance and quality.

Sligo and Dublin are characterised by temperate maritime climates and are particularly vulnerable to

intensified storms, coastal and land flooding, and rising sea levels due to their coastal settings and reliance on aging stormwater infrastructure (Table 1) [13]. Heavy rainfall events lead to flash flooding, mobilizing contaminants such as agricultural runoff, sewage, and industrial pollutants [14,15]. Coastal erosion and strained stormwater infrastructure further amplify contamination risks in Dublin [16]. In contrast, Vilanova i la Geltrú and Benidorm, situated in the Mediterranean region, face warmer temperatures, droughts, and heatwaves [17]. Drought exacerbates water scarcity and concentrates contaminants, while heatwaves heighten the risk of algal blooms and microbial contamination, impacting tourism and water systems. Benidorm’s reliance on tourism increases the presence of contaminants like microplastics, while Vilanova i la Geltrú faces pressures from agricultural runoff.

Oarsoaldea, as an industrialized coastal region in the Bay of Biscay, face unique contamination risks, including heavy metals and industrial pollutants mobilized by heavy rainfall and sea-level rise. Its steep topography and coastal infrastructure further compound these challenges. Massa, located along the Tyrrhenian coast, is highly susceptible to coastal erosion, storm surges, and coastal and land flooding, which increase the mobilization of pollutants from industrial and agricultural sources, particularly in low-lying areas near the coastline [18,19]. Droughts increase contaminant concentrations

Table 1

Key climate-related hazards and contamination risks in study coastal cities.

Coastal city	Unique characteristics	Key climate-related hazards	Key contamination risks
Sligo (Ireland)	Exposure to open Atlantic Ocean, small-scale city, large rural hinterland, heavy rely on agricultural activities and natural landscapes	Intensified storms, coastal and land flooding, rising sea levels	Agricultural runoff, sewage, industrial pollutants
Dublin (Ireland)	Sheltered by Dublin Bay, capital city, highly urbanized setting, dense population, extensive aging infrastructure	Intensified storms, coastal and land flooding, rising sea levels	Agricultural runoff, sewage, industrial pollutants
Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain)	Mediterranean climate, mid-size city, agricultural and tourism pressures	Warmer temperatures, droughts, heatwaves	Concentrated contaminants, algal blooms, microbial contamination, agricultural runoff
Benidorm (Spain)	Mediterranean climate, major tourism hub, arid conditions, reliance on desalination for water resources	Warmer temperatures, droughts, heatwaves	Concentrated contaminants, algal blooms, microplastics
Oarsoaldea (Spain)	Bay of Biscay, intense Atlantic storms, industrialized coastal region, steep topography, high rainfall variability	Heavy rainfall, sea-level rise, industrial and heavy metal contamination	Industrial pollutants, heavy metals
Massa (Italy)	Tyrrhenian coast, low-lying areas	Coastal erosion, storm surges, coastal and land flooding, droughts	Industrial and agricultural pollutants
Oeiras (Portugal)	Near Tagus river estuary, Atlantic tides and storm surges, urban development, aging wastewater systems	Land flooding, storm surges, coastal flooding and erosion	Industrial and urban runoff
Piran (Slovenia)	Adriatic coast, historic city centre, tourism dependency, limited freshwater resources	Droughts, flash floods, untreated wastewater discharges	Untreated wastewater discharges
Gdansk (Poland)	Baltic sea, severe winter storms, low salinity waters, large industrial port city	Sea-level rise, pluvial and coastal flooding	Industrial pollutants, port and urban runoff
Samsun (Türkiye)	Black sea, steep terrain, agricultural lands	Intense storms, heavy rainfall, coastal erosion, sea-level rise	Agricultural and industrial pollutants

in water bodies, complicating contamination management. Similarly, Oeiras, situated near the Tagus River estuary, faces land flooding and storm surges that exacerbate coastal flooding and erosion. Industrial activity, urban development, and aging wastewater systems amplify contamination risks [20,21].

Piran, a small Adriatic coastal city heavily dependent on tourism, is particularly sensitive to contamination risks such as untreated wastewater discharges during peak seasons [3,22]. Droughts and flash floods further exacerbate these vulnerabilities, especially around the historic Tartini Square. Gdansk, a major industrial port city on the Baltic Sea, is highly exposed to sea-level rise and pluvial and coastal flooding, which lead to contamination from industrial sites and aging infrastructure [23,24]. Pollutants from the port and urban areas pose ongoing challenges to water quality management [25,26]. Lastly, Samsun, located along the Black Sea, experiences intense storms, heavy rainfall and coastal erosion. Its steep terrain accelerates the transport of

agricultural and industrial pollutants into the sea, threatening freshwater and marine ecosystems [27], whereas sea-level rise and coastal erosion threaten coastal agricultural lands [28].

Impact of extreme weather events on contaminant fate and transport

Extreme weather events disrupt biogeochemical processes in coastal environments [29]. These events, exacerbated by climate change, mobilize pollutants from various sources, altering their movement in both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. Fig. 2 outlines the sequential relationships between climate-related hazards, interim processes, and water quality alteration processes, highlighting the interconnected pathways through which climate-driven hazards affect coastal ecosystems and human health.

Coastal and land flooding, driven by intense rainfall and storm surges, mobilizes contaminants from agriculture, industry, and urban areas into waterways, increasing

Figure 2

Cascading impacts of extreme weather events on water quality in coastal cities.

waterborne pollution risks [30,*31]. In Dublin and Sligo, heavy rainfall events have led to widespread land flooding, which in turn has resulted in the overflow of untreated sewage and agricultural runoff into waterways [32]. Flooding overwhelms stormwater systems, causing contaminants such as nitrates, phosphates, pathogens, and heavy metals to be flushed into rivers and coastal waters [33]. These contaminants can lead to eutrophication—a process where excess nutrients in water bodies stimulate algal blooms, depleting oxygen levels and harming aquatic systems—causing long-term declines in biodiversity. In Gdansk, flooding due to sea-level rise and heavy rainfall mobilizes industrial pollutants, including petrochemicals and heavy metals, into the Baltic Sea [34], where they accumulate in sediments and persist for decades, impacting benthic organisms and disrupting food chains [35]. In Samsun, agricultural runoff during heavy rainfall contributes to nutrient loading and pesticide contamination in the Black Sea. This nutrient influx, accelerated by the steep topography surrounding Samsun, promotes algal blooms that deplete oxygen levels, threatening fish populations and biodiversity while creating conditions for toxin-producing cyanobacteria harmful to public health.

Droughts and heatwaves in Mediterranean cities like Benidorm and Vilanova i la Geltrú concentrate contaminants in water bodies [36]. In Benidorm, water scarcity caused by prolonged droughts concentrates contaminants from tourism-related activities, including pharmaceuticals, personal care products, and microplastics, in coastal waters [37,38]. These contaminants, combined with the effects of higher temperatures, can alter the chemical composition of water, increasing the toxicity of pollutants and facilitating their

bioaccumulation—the accumulation of toxic substances in the tissues of organisms over time—in marine organisms, which can affect higher trophic levels, including humans [39,40]. In some cases, droughts have led to the drying of wetlands and other natural water filters, reducing the ecosystem's ability to mitigate pollution naturally. Similarly, in Vilanova i la Geltrú, the combination of heatwaves, drought conditions and agricultural runoff concentrate fertilizers and pesticides in rivers and coastal waters, increasing the risk of eutrophication and toxic algal blooms [12]. The loss of wetlands further diminishes natural filtration systems, leading to long-term degradation of water quality and ecosystem services. This is particularly concerning for cities reliant on tourism.

Storm surges erode coastal areas and mobilize contaminants from sediments and landfills [41,42]. In Oarsoaldea, legacy pollutants from former industrial activity such as heavy metals are resuspended into the water column during storm events, posing risks to local fisheries and marine biodiversity. Long-term exposure to these contaminants can lead to reproductive and developmental issues in marine species, ultimately disrupting the ecological balance. In Massa, storm surges and coastal erosion release heavy metals, plastics, and organic pollutants from landfills and other waste disposal sites located near the shoreline into the Tyrrhenian Sea, posing persisting risks to marine life and human health through the contamination of seafood [43]. Storm surges also undermine coastal defences, making it more difficult to prevent further contamination in future events. In Piran, the Adriatic Sea's rising water levels combined with storm surges increase the risk of saltwater intrusion and contamination of

freshwater resources. As Piran is a popular tourist destination, the contamination of coastal waters not only impacts marine ecosystems but also threatens the local economy, which is heavily dependent on tourism [22].

Sea-level rise, combined with urbanization, exacerbates contamination risks [44]. In Oeiras, rising sea levels and coastal flooding threaten low-lying wastewater treatment facilities, leading to the discharge of untreated sewage into the Tagus River estuary and the Atlantic Ocean, posing long-term health risks [45]. Similarly, in Gdansk, the combination of sea-level rise and increased storm activity puts pressure on the city’s aging infrastructure, leading to more frequent contamination events. The flooding of industrial areas and stormwater systems introduces heavy metals, chemicals, and pathogens into the Baltic Sea, where they accumulate in sediments, disrupting marine ecosystems and increasing the risk of bioaccumulation.

Mitigation and adaptation strategies

To address contamination risks heightened by climate change, coastal cities must adopt a combination of mitigation and adaptation strategies. These include monitoring systems, infrastructure improvements, and effective policy frameworks to enhance resilience to extreme weather events (Table 2). While the strategies discussed here have shown promise, their implementation is often constrained by economic costs, governance challenges, and the need for active community involvement to ensure success.

Real-time monitoring and early warning systems are critical for tracking water quality and pollutant levels

during extreme weather events [46,47]. In Dublin, the installation of real-time water quality sensors in urban rivers has been essential for monitoring pollutants during heavy rainfall events [48]. These systems allow for the early detection of pollution spikes and the implementation of rapid response measures, and the identification of vulnerable areas where stormwater overflows are likely to occur, helping to prioritize infrastructure upgrades [46]. Similarly, the Baltic Sea Monitoring Program in Gdansk provides valuable data on marine water quality in response to flooding and industrial runoff, promoting cross-city and cross-border collaboration for coastal monitoring. However, such systems require significant investment in technology and expertise, posing financial and logistical barriers for cities with limited resources. Additionally, ensuring the long-term sustainability of these systems often depends on stable funding and effective integration into local governance frameworks. Expanding monitoring networks across European coastal cities is vital for improving adaptive capacity but must also address the challenge of data accessibility and interoperability among stakeholders. Investment in real-time water quality monitoring, remote sensing technologies, and predictive models can enhance cities’ ability to anticipate and respond to contamination risks during extreme weather events.

Sustainable urban drainage systems (SUDS) and green infrastructure reduce flood risks and stormwater contamination by allowing natural absorption and filtration [49]. Oarsoaldea has been a leader in adopting green infrastructure to combat flooding and contamination risks [50]. The city has implemented

Table 2

Comparative summary of mitigation strategies for coastal cities, including descriptions, examples of implementation, and associated challenges.

Mitigation/Adaptation strategy	Description	City examples	Challenges
Real-time monitoring and early warning systems	Installation of sensors to track water quality and pollutant levels during extreme weather events.	Dublin: sensors detect pollution spikes. Gdansk: Baltic sea monitoring system.	High costs, data interoperability issues.
Green infrastructure and SUDS	Use of nature-based solutions like wetlands, green roofs, and permeable pavements to manage stormwater and filter pollutants.	Oarsoaldea: Wetlands and permeable pavements. Oeiras: Bioswales and urban wetlands.	Land-use constraints; limited public awareness of benefits.
Wastewater treatment upgrades	Investments in infrastructure to handle increased water volumes and emerging contaminants.	Samsun: Upgrades prevent untreated releases. Benidorm: Advanced treatment for pharmaceuticals and microplastics.	Expensive to implement and maintain; requires long-term political commitment.
Nature-based solutions (e.g., wetland and dune restoration)	Restoration of natural buffers to filter pollutants and protect against storm surges and erosion.	Piran: Wetlands filter nutrients. Massa: Coastal dunes stabilize shorelines.	Scalability limited by land-use conflicts and long-term maintenance needs.
Cross-border collaboration and EU initiatives/projects	Collaborative efforts to monitor and manage transboundary pollution and flooding risks.	Gdansk: Baltic sea cross-border monitoring. SCORE project: All cities participate in co-creation of climate resilience strategies.	Governance challenges for international cooperation and project scalability.

permeable pavements and green roofs, and constructed wetlands to manage stormwater runoff in flood-prone areas. These solutions help filter contaminants such as heavy metals and nutrients before they enter rivers and coastal waters, reducing the overall pollutant load and protecting ecosystems from degradation. Similarly, Oeiras has embraced green infrastructure solutions to reduce the impacts of heavy rainfall and storm surges. The city's use of rain gardens, bioswales, and urban wetlands has not only mitigated flood risks but also improved local biodiversity by creating habitats for wildlife. By capturing and filtering stormwater before it reaches the Tagus River estuary, these systems help prevent contaminant buildup in the water, benefiting both human health and marine ecosystems. To enhance resilience to extreme weather events, coastal cities should continue to invest in SUDS and green infrastructure. Moreover, they are cost-effective and adaptable to a wide range of urban environments, making them a key tool in mitigating the effects of climate change on contamination. However, replicating successful SUDS designs across cities requires customization to local climatic, geographic, and socio-economic conditions, which can increase complexity and costs, and their widespread adoption is often hindered by land-use constraints, maintenance needs, and limited public awareness of their benefits.

Aging infrastructure in many coastal cities cannot cope with the increasing water volumes from floods and storms [51,52,53]. Samsun, located on the Black Sea coast, has recently invested in upgrading its wastewater treatment infrastructure to address the growing risk of stormwater overflows. These upgrades are accompanied by the installation of backup power systems to ensure continued operation during extreme weather events, reducing the risk of untreated wastewater being released into the Black Sea. In Benidorm, where water scarcity and wastewater management have become critical concerns due to prolonged droughts, the city has invested in wastewater recycling and desalination plants [54]. These facilities are helping to alleviate water shortages while reducing the pressure on natural water sources, thus lowering the risk of contamination during droughts. Additionally, the city has implemented advanced wastewater treatment technologies to remove emerging contaminants, such as pharmaceuticals and personal care products, which are often concentrated during periods of low water flow. Investing in resilient wastewater and stormwater infrastructure is crucial for protecting coastal cities from climate-driven contamination risks, although the costs associated with upgrading aging systems can be a significant barrier, particularly for cities with limited fiscal capacity [51]. Moreover, these upgrades should be designed with future climate scenarios in mind, ensuring that cities are prepared for both the increased intensity of extreme weather events and the evolving patterns of water usage

and pollution, which requires long-term planning and political commitment.

Nature-based solutions (NbS), such as restoring wetlands and dunes, are essential for protecting coastal cities from erosion and storm surges while filtering contaminants [55–57]. Piran has implemented NbS by restoring its coastal wetlands, which serve as natural buffers against storm surges. These wetlands not only absorb excess water during storms but also filter out pollutants such as nutrients, heavy metals, and organic contaminants, improving water quality in the Adriatic Sea. In Massa, the restoration of coastal dunes and the implementation of living shorelines have helped to protect the city from coastal erosion and storm damage. These NbS projects stabilize the coastline and reduce the transport of contaminants into the Tyrrhenian Sea, while also creating new habitats for marine and coastal species. By leveraging the protective and filtering capacities of natural habitats, coastal cities can enhance their resilience to climate change while addressing contamination risks in a sustainable and cost-effective manner [58]. Notwithstanding, these approaches can face challenges in scalability and replicability due to land-use conflicts, competing economic interests, and the need for long-term maintenance. Political barriers and limited stakeholder buy-in can further hinder the adoption of NbS, especially in areas where immediate economic benefits are not apparent.

Effective governance and policy frameworks are essential for scaling up climate adaptation strategies [29,59,60]. In Gdansk, the city's flood risk management strategy is closely linked to Poland's national climate adaptation plan and the European Union's Water Framework Directive [61]. By integrating these frameworks, Gdansk has been able to secure funding for flood defence projects, enhance cross-border cooperation on water quality monitoring, and implement stricter regulations on industrial pollution. Similarly, Dublin has developed a comprehensive climate action plan that addresses both flood risk and contamination management. The city's approach combines infrastructure improvements, community engagement, and regional partnerships to reduce climate vulnerabilities and improve water quality. Dublin's active participation in the European Climate Adaptation Platform (Climate-ADAPT) ensures that the city's policies are aligned with the latest climate science and best practices for managing climate risks. Effective governance and policy frameworks are essential for scaling up successful mitigation and adaptation strategies [62]. Coastal cities must prioritize cross-sectoral collaboration, secure funding for climate-resilient infrastructure, and actively engage with international climate adaptation initiatives to ensure that their responses to climate change are robust and sustainable [58,63]. Community-based initiatives and stakeholder involvement are particularly

valuable in this vein. Local NGOs, residents, and community groups can play an active role in monitoring, maintaining, and advocating for these measures. For example, participatory approaches, such as the implementation of Coastal City Living Labs, can enhance local engagement, improve data collection and monitoring, and reduce operational costs [**50].

Future research should prioritize the study of understudied contaminants, such as pharmaceuticals, pesticides, and microplastics, to better understand their behaviour under extreme weather conditions and their long-term impacts on ecosystems and human health [**5,6]. Additionally, research focusing on the co-benefits and trade-offs of integrating nature-based solutions with existing infrastructure would provide valuable insights into scalable and replicable adaptation strategies [**55–57].

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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- * of special interest
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